
Agricultural Fertilizer Consumption in Sangli District (Maharashtra)

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15044564

Abstract:

Fertilizers have a key role to play in transforming agriculture. Adoption of improved seeds, fertilizers and irrigation systems has led to a significant increase in food production in Indian agriculture. Both chemical and organic fertilizers increase agricultural production. The use of fertilizers in agriculture and the development of agriculture depends on crop productivity, irrigation methods, soils properties and crop characteristics. A recent study investigated the geographical distribution of agricultural fertilizer use in Sangli district of Maharashtra. The data required for this research was taken from the Socio-Economic Analysis of Sangli District 2023-24. Q-GIS software was used to prepare the data. Significant regional disparities in fertilizer use were found.

Keywords: *Fertilizer Consumption, Agricultural Productivity, Spatial Analysis.*

Introduction:

Organic and chemical fertilizers are considered essential for the growth and development of crops. If this element is involved in the metabolic processes of crops and without this element, the crop cannot complete its life cycle (Havlin, Beaton, Tisdale, Nelson 2010). Fertilizers play an important role in the growth and proper development of crops and in order to obtain higher yields from agriculture. Fertilizer is an important input for the expansion of agricultural production, if excessive fertilizer is used in any farm, it affects the agricultural production capacity and soil properties. However, high levels of fertilizer use have been observed in the study area, therefore, to analyse the fertilizer use in agriculture, necessary data has been collected through the schedule and depiction of fertilizer use in that region for the soil degradation area. In Sangli district, there is significant regional variation in fertilizer use. A spatial analysis of fertilizer use for

the year 2023-24 has been done tehsil-wise. The objective of this study is to analyse the distribution of fertilizer use in agriculture in various tehsils of Sangli district of Maharashtra and to understand the factors affecting this pattern

Study Area:

Sangli district is a part of the southern districts of the state of Maharashtra and the Deccan plateau. Geographically, it is located between 16⁰ 45' and 17⁰ 33' N latitude and 73⁰ 42' and 75⁰ 40' E longitude. The average elevation of the district is 553 m above sea level. It is bounded on the north by Satara and Solapur districts, on the east and south by the state of Karnataka, on the southwest by Kolhapur district and on the west by Ratnagiri district. Sangli district extends 205 km from north to south and 96 km from east to west. The geographical area of Sangli district is 8572 sq. km. and its total population is 28, 22,143 according to the 2011 census, where 14, 35,728 Males and

13, 86,415 females population were observed. The total literacy rate of Sangli district is 82.62 percent and the population density is 329 per sq. km. Administratively Sangli district is divided into three subdivisions mainly i.e. Walwa, Miraj and Khanapur and the district has ten tehsils such as Walwa, Shirala, Miraj, Jat, Atpadi, Khanapur, Palus, Kavathe-Mahankal, Tasgaon and Kadegaon.

Map No. 1

Objectives:

An attempt has been made to study the use of fertilizer on agricultural land in the study area.

Database and methodology:

The present research paper depends on secondary data. The fertilizer consumption data were collected for the analysis from the Socio-economic review of Sangli district 2023-24. The analysis of the

data has been done with the help of the following formula, which was created by M. G. Jadhav and S. D. Shinde (1979) to enumerate concentration index values for fertilizer consumption per unit area. The formula is slightly modified here as,

$$I_{fe} = \frac{TF}{DF} \times 100$$

Where,

I_{fe} = Index of fertilizer consumption.

Tf = per hect/ Kg fertilizer consumption in the tehsil.

Df = per hect/Kg. fertilizer consumption in the district.

Result and Discussion:

The total fertilizer use in Sangli district was 539.30 kg/ha in 2023-24. To show the fertilizer use in agriculture in Sangli district, it has been divided into three categories, namely high fertilizer use, medium fertilizer use and low fertilizer use.

Spatial Pattern of Fertilizer Consumption: High Fertilizer Consumption (Above 250 kg/ha):

This includes Palus tehsil located on the banks of Krishna River. Palus tehsil has the highest fertilizer use at 278.95 kg/ha. Cash crops like sugarcane, oilseeds and fruits and vegetables are dominant in Palus tehsil. Palus tehsil has sugar factories and irrigation facilities are well developed. Apart from this, farmers are socially and economically capable of adopting new agricultural technologies in their farming. As a result, Palus tehsil has the highest fertilizer use in the entire Sangli district.

Table No 1: Sangli District: Fertilizer Consumption Index Value 2023-24

Sr. No.	Regions	Fertilizer Index Value (kg/hector)	Tehsils
1	High Fertilizer Consumption	Above 250	Palus
2	Moderate Fertilizer Consumption	125 - 250	Walwa, Shirala, Kadegaon Khanapur, Miraj,
3	Low Fertilizer Consumption	Below 125	K-Mahankal, Atpadi, Tasgaon, Jath

Source: Calculation Based on Socio-Economic Review of Sangli District 2023-24

Moderate Fertilizer Consumption (125 kg/ha to 250 kg/ha):

In medium fertilizer use, Walwa, Shirala, Kadegaon, Khanapur and Miraj tehsils are shown in this category. The index values are 129.47 kg/ha, 189.30 kg/ha, 155.18 kg/ha, 132.6 kg/ha and 139.62 kg/ha respectively. These tehsils are all developed through irrigation. Therefore, both these tehsils have areas of sugarcane cultivation and fruit cultivation. Fertilizer use is moderate due to generally good soil quality. In addition, cooperative sectors have played an important role in increasing the use of fertilizers in these tehsils, hence farmers are aware about the use of fertilizers in agricultural land.

Map. No. 2

Low Fertilizer Consumption (Below 125 kg/ha):

The tehsils with low fertilizer use include, Kavathe-Mahankal, Atpadi, Tasgaon and Jath. While Kavathe-Mahankal (107.23 kg ha), Atpadi (88.92 kg ha), Tasgaon (85.89 kg ha), Jath (25.2 kg ha) tehsils are eastern part of Sangli district, drought-affected areas, lack of irrigation facilities and the economic condition of farmers is very low. That's way the fertilizer consumption is low in 2023-24.

Conclusion:

Organic fertilizers or chemical fertilizers are considered as important tools to increase agricultural production. In the last few decades, the use of various types of

fertilizers has increased in Sangli district. There has been a significant change in the irrigation area in Sangli district, then there has been a significant increase in the development of lift irrigation, well irrigation canals. Krishna River due to favourable irrigation and soil conditions, and in some tehsils due to public awareness in the use of fertilizers and soil degradation, the use of fertilizers has also decreased to a certain extent. On the contrary, in the eastern tehsils, the use is less due to underdeveloped irrigation system, infrastructure development facilities and challenging natural and soil conditions. This highlights the need for targeted agricultural policies to remove regional disparities and optimize the use of fertilizers for satisfactory productivity in agriculture.

References:

1. Jadhav, M. G. (1979). Spatio-Temporal Developments in Fertilizer Consumption of Sangli District., Journal of Shivaji University, Kolhapur, 45-48.
2. Tandon, H. L. (1995). Fertilizer and Integrated Nutrient Recommendations for Balance and Efficiency, Fertilizer Development and Consultation Organization. New Delhi.
3. Socio-Economic Survey of Sangli District, (2023-24). Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Maharashtra Mumbai.
4. SeetaPrabhu, K. (1987). Pesticides Use in Indian Agriculture. Bombay: Himalaya Publishing House.
5. Jalan, M. L. (1987). Marketing of Agricultural Inputs. Bombay: Himalaya Publishing House.
6. More, A. V. Spatio Distribution of Agricultural Fertilizer Consumption in Sangli District (Maharashtra), International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) Volume 13 Issue 8, pp. 1542-1544
7. Winfried, V., Erbard, K. (1976). The Development and Fertilizer Production and Use in India., Applied Sciences and Development.